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The Relationship among Job Stress and Job Satisfaction in Municipality Personnel

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Abstract:

The purpose of this quantitative study investigates the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction. The sample consists of public municipality personnel from Chennai in India. The results show there is a significant negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction. The result also shows that there isn't significant difference between two genders in job stress and job satisfaction. Using the randomization sampling technique a total of 200 participants were selected as a sample of from that organization. The participants in answering the job stress and job satisfaction questionnaire.

Introduction:

Organization plays an extremely important role in the development of country. One of the key factor success in organization is able human resource. For received in this aim is necessary personnel have high level satisfaction. Job life is one of the important parts of our daily lives which cause a great deal of stress. Due to the competitive nature of the job environment most of the people in the world are spending their time for job related work purposes resulting ignore the stressor those are influencing their work and life. Usually people are more worry about their outcome of their work that can even affect the way they treat other people and how they communicate with their peers and customers. For example, people with a higher percentage of occupational stress may not be satisfied with their job and therefore they will not feel happy working in the organization. They may feel frustrated or when they are having problems with customers. This may leave a negative impact to the organization itself. Therefore, it is very important for employer and employees to realize the stress and the stressor that cause all the negative effects.

Literature Review:

Numerous studies found that stress influences the employees' job satisfaction and their overall performance in their work. Because most of the organizations now are more demanding for the better job outcomes. In fact, modern times have been called as the "**age of anxiety and stress**"(Coleman 1976). The stress itself will be affected by number of stressors. Stressors do occur within the environment of the organization. Workplace stress occurs when individuals are confronted with a situation in which coping intervention are inadequate and their bodies are unable to adapt.

Nevertheless, **Beehr and new man (1978)** had defined stress as a situation which will force a person to deviate from normal functioning due to the change in his/her psychological or physiological condition, such that the person is forced to deviate from normal functioning. From the definition that has been identified by researchers, we can conclude that it is truly important from an individual to recognize the stresses that are facing by them in their career.

According to **Lasky (1995)** demands associated with family and finances can be a major source of 'extra organizational' stress that can complicate, or even precipitate, work place stress.

Russo & vitaliano (1995) that the occurrence of a stressor in the work place either immediately following a period of chronic stress at home, or in co- junction with other major life stressors, is likely to have a marked impact on outcome.

Objectives of study:

- ❖ To identify the factors that influences the job satisfaction.
- ❖ To offer valuable suggestions to improve the satisfaction level of employees.
- ❖ To study about ways that the managers or employers can reduce the job stress.
- ❖ To describe the ways in which the stress affects physical health and life style.
- ❖ To understand the principles and applications of the mindfulness based cognitive strategies.

Scope of the study:

- ✓ The study helps us to understand that good management and good work organization are the best forms of stress prevention.
- ✓ The analysis is helpful in assessing the extend of stress experienced by the employees.
- ✓ This study helps to identify the employer's level of satisfaction towards welfare measure.

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- ✓ This study is helpful to the organization for identifying the area of dissatisfaction job of the employees.
- ✓ This study helps to get the feedback from the employees towards their job.

Limitation of the study:

- This survey is subjected to the bias and prejudices of the respondents hence 100% accuracy cannot be assured.
- An employee has fear to reveal the negative aspects.
- The information collected is based on the perception of the respondents.
- The study ignores important root causes of stress.
- During the collection of the data many employees were unwilling to fill the questionnaire due to the lack of time.

Job Stress:

Job stress is the extent to which employees feel a tension of anxiety caused by their jobs'. Job stress can also be defined as "the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker.

Any job has a potential for some type of stressor, whether the stressor are motivators promoting one to succeed or overwhelm one causing lowered self esteem and damage to one life. Although stresses are identified in the work setting the level of stress experienced can only be determined by the individual who has experienced the stressor. The impact of work stress can seriously affect the organization and employee.

Job satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's or job experiences". Job satisfaction may be examined as part of the construct of employee engagement, as it is a combination of job involvement, organizational commitment and intentions to stay. In contrast the confusion contradiction and interchange of terms for engagement raise the question as to whether employee's engagement is a valid and reliable construct at all.

Engagement is a predictor of work behavior and overall performance. Engaged employees are more profitable to the organization, customer focused, safer employees and much more likely to withstand the temptation to leave. There are four primary factors that determine job satisfaction. The first factor is for the individual employee to have mentally challenging work. The second factor is equitable rewards where employees monetary systems and policies that are in line with their expectations.

The third factor is supportive working conditions. The fourth factor is to have supportive colleagues and "having friendly and supportive co-workers leads to increases job satisfaction". Within the framework of job satisfaction, Herzberg's Theory of Motivation, a two-dimensional paradigm of factors affecting work attitudes can be regarded as a theory base for job satisfaction.

Factors such as supervision, interpersonal relations, working conditions and salary are hygiene factors rather than motivating factors related to overall job satisfaction. Motivating factors such as achievement, recognition, responsibility and advancement are considered to be strong determinants of job satisfaction. The Theory of Motivation relates to the definition of job satisfaction, whereas, a pleasurable and positive state within the work environment gives rise of appraisal for the individual worker. The Theory of Motivation explains factors such as hygiene and motivation that coincide with job satisfaction. Overall, employee satisfaction whether it a physician, a staff related to retention has become a major issue for today and in the future. According to Randstad's Employee Review, there must be a strong foundation of communication, trust and loyalty, if not companies can anticipate a mass shuffle of people and jobs when the present job market and economy rebound.

One of the affective factors in municipality personnel job satisfaction in India is workload and many clients. Increase workload and client was lead job stress product and redact job satisfaction. Discovered that if municipality employees 'career orientations fit their positions, they have higher job satisfaction. Moreover, municipality personnel managers' personal characteristics positively affect their job satisfaction. After all, if municipality personnel professionals are satisfied with their jobs, they have stronger organizational commitment and subsequently lower level of turnover intentions. In the study conducted equity between technical and managerial employees is the key factor for municipality personnel professionals' job satisfaction. Focused on Chennai municipality personnel employees, **Solaimannezhad** found that individual demographic characteristics such as marital status, age, position title and annual salary affect employees' satisfaction.

Review Previous Study:

Several studies have tried to determine the link between stress and job satisfaction. Job satisfaction and job stress are the two hot focuses in human resource management researches. According to the researches job satisfaction has been found significant relationship with job stress. One study of general practitioners in England identified four job stressors that were predictive of job dissatisfaction. In other study, stated that organization factors such as workload and working condition were negatively related with job satisfaction. Fletcher and Payne identified that a lack of satisfaction can be a source of stress, while high satisfaction can alleviate the effects of stress. This study reveals that, both of job stress and job satisfaction were found to be interrelated. The study of Landsbergis showed that high levels of work stress are associated with low levels of job satisfaction. Moreover, Cummins have emphasized that job stressors are predictive of jobs dissatisfaction and greater propensity to leave the organization. In this study, we would like to examine what extent of interrelation between the job stress and job satisfaction among Chennai municipality personnel in India.

Research Purpose and Aim:

The purpose of this study was assessed the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction in Chennai municipality personnel in India.

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between role conflict and job stress.

Hypothesis2: There is a relationship between workload pressure and job stress.

Hypothesis3: There is a relationship between job role ambiguity and job stress.

Hypothesis 4: There is a relationship between performance pressure and job stress.

Hypothesis 5: There is a negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 6: There is deference between two genders in job stress and job satisfaction.

Materials and Methods:

Sample:

This study was conducted in a Chennai municipality ninth area in India.

Using the random selection sampling technique, a total of 200 respondents were selected as a sample of the study from that municipality. The respondents come from various employees' technical parts and official parts and city service parts Chennai municipality in order to give better mixture between respondents to increase the generalization of the result. The response rate was 67.66% which was very much acceptable in social science research. The participants were 62.56% female and 37.44% male with mean age of 37.6 years. More than 50% of them were married (107 respondent or 52.71%), 71 single, 17 separated, 8 divorced.

Measurements:

Variable measurements employed in this study are well defined and developed tools from previous studies. Job stress is measured by "Job Stress Questionnaire, JSQ" proposed by Caplan, this scale include four dimensions, namely work load, role conflict, role ambiguity and performance pressure which comprised thirteen items. Each of job stressors was measured one a six-point Likert Scale in rich indicated "strongly disagree", indicated, disagree, indicated "somewhat disagree", indicated "somewhat agree", indicated, agree and indicated "strongly agree". The main reason for this choice of all six job stressor was widely included aspects stress in job environment. Part 2 includes job satisfaction which is measured using Job Descriptive Index (JDI) A reliable facet measure over time, applicable across variety of demographic groups and measured on a six point scale with least satisfied(one) to very satisfied (six). The structure this section differed from previous studies insofar as it considered satisfaction as a positive phenomenon. Consequently, there was no facility for dissatisfaction. Part 3 includes a number of demographical questions such as gender, age, marital status, race, and education level.

Data Analysis Method:

Various statistical methods have been employed to compare the data collected from 200 respondents. These methods include description analysis and regression analysis. Each method has used to analysis the relationship of different variables.

Firstly, Descriptive analysis refers to the transformation of raw data into a form that would provide information to describe a set of factors in a situation that will make them easy to understand and interpret. This analysis will be given information for the data through the frequency distribution, central tendency and the dispersion. Data are collected on demographic variables are processed and reported in percentages.

Secondly, multiple regression analysis is an extension of bivariate regression analysis, which allows for the simultaneous investigation of the effect of two or more independent variable on a single interval scale dependent variable. The dependent variable for this study is Jobs satisfaction, whose types of measurement are interval. For this study, there are several independent variables relating to job satisfaction and job stress whose types of measurement are interval and simultaneously investigates the several independent variables single variable a multiple linear regression is fitted for these variables.

Results:

The Results of Hypothesis 1:

Most research suggests that role conflict is indeed negatively correlated with job satisfaction, job involvement, performance, tension, propensity to leave the job and job performance variables.

Table 1: Regression Results

Variables	Beta	t-value	p-value
Role conflict	.02	.34	.72
Workload pressure	.36	5.47	.0001d
Role ambiguity	.07	1	.31
Performance pressure	.21	2.96	.003

Table 2: summary of Regression Analysis Effects of Job stress toward job satisfaction.

Regression Statistics	F- value	P-value	Adj-R2	B
Values	15.57	.003	%7	-.27

Table 3: Deference between male and female in job stress and job satisfaction.

Variables	Gender	Mean	Standard Division	T-value	DF	p-value
Job stress	Male	33.4	8.7	.53	198	.6
	Female	34.1	8.9			
Job satisfaction	Male	67.93	12.79	.94	198	.29
	Female	69.86	11.4			

The Result of Hypothesis 2:

Several studies have highlighted the deleterious consequences of high workloads or work overload. As expected, the results of this study shows that the relationship between workload pressure and job stress is significant with $\beta=0.36$ ($p=0.0001$).

The Result of Hypothesis 3:

The result of this study shows that the association between role ambiguity and job stress is not significant with $\beta=0.07$ ($p=0.31$)

The Result of Hypothesis 4:

The support of H4 is in line with the results found multiple regression analysis shows relative advantage having $\beta=0.21$ ($p=0.003$) is the strongest predictor of job stress.

The Result of Hypothesis 5:

Regress results are shown Tables 2. Table 2 depicts the computer F-value and R square to understand the overall significance of the regression model. Research model yielding significant p-values ($p < 0.003$) and R square around 7 percent of the variance in job satisfaction was explained.

The result of Hypothesis 6:

To support hypothesis 6 we also used T-test analysis to understand the deference of job stress and job satisfaction between males and females.

Conclusion:

Based on the finding of the study, there are a few key points that can be used to conclude this research paper. It is very important that the municipalities understands the needs of its employees and provide what is best for the employees. Constant appraisal programs and appreciation should be given to reinstate and motivate the employees. Motivation is a key factor as well in affecting job stress among employees. Employees who are highly motivated will fell happier and are more willing to work for the organizations.

Municipality should have been continuously developing employee's potential. The factors of satisfaction with workload and professional support, municipality should allocate time suitable to workload and should provide well training for supervisor to coaching and supervise their subordinate and setup course for team building.

References:

- **Mahdad, A., 2006.** Industrial and organizational psychology, jungle institute, pp4.
- Gallup Organization, 2008. Employee engagement. Retrieved February 19.
- **Syptak, J., D. Marsland and D. Ulmer, 1999.** Job satisfaction: Putting their into practice. Family practice Management. 6(9): 26-30. Retrieved January 16.
- **Delavar, A., 2010,** Educational and psychological research, Virayesh publication Institute pp4.
- **Van Sell, M., A.P. Brief and R.S. Schuler, 1981.** Managing Job stress, Little Brown and Company. Boston, MA,
- **Townley, G., 2000.** Long hourculture causing economy to suffer, Management Accounting.
- **Rode, J.C, 2004.** Job satisfaction and life satisfaction revisited: A long itudinal test of an integrated model, human relations.
- **Fletcher, J.B and R.payne, 1980.** Stress and work: A review and a theoretical framework,
- **Smith,P.C, I.M. Kendall and C.I HULIN, 1969.** Measurement of satisfaction in work and retirement, Rand-MC Nally, Chicago, IL.
- **Chan, K.B, G.Lai, Y.C.KO and K.W.Boey, 2000.** Work stress among six professional groups.
- **Rizzo, J.R.,R.J.House and S.I.Lirtzman, 1970.** Role conflict and ambiguity in complex organizations, administrative science.
- **Cummins,R.C., 1990.** Job stress and the buffering effort of supervisory support, Group and organization studies.